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SMART CITY AS AN ALTERNATIVE SOLUTION FOR URBAN DEVELOPMENT AND EQUITY IN INDONESIA

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ADIWIDYA 9 | #SINERGIKANPERAN
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Development of *Chlorella vulgaris* Microalgae Photobioreactor System to Optimize the Production of Oxygen (O₂) Concentration and to Mitigate the abundant Carbon Dioxide (CO₂)

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Abstract. *Chlorella vulgaris* Microalgae photobioreactor to optimize the production Oxygen (O₂) concentration has been developed. The photobioreactor consisted of temperature control using LM35 Sensors, Oxygen concentration measuring device using SK-25F sensor and the *Chlorella vulgaris* photobioreactor itself which were integrated in a system. The Photobioreactor was illuminated by halogen lamp and Blue LED. Not only being illuminated by varying light source but it was also set in condition without light (0 lux), so the difference of Oxygen concentration that was produced in every light condition with different light intensities can be examined. photobioreactor has two tubes containing 1250 ml microalgae *Chlorella vulgaris*. The first tube is supplied by CO₂ gas with flow rate 0.5 l / min and the second tube is not supplied by CO₂ gas. The intensity of halogen lamp has varied at 1000 lux, 3000 lux and 5000 lux, meanwhile Blue LED was 1065 lux. Temperature control successfully maintained the photobioreactor temperature in the range 25 °C - 35 °C. The maximum concentration production of O₂ gas was 21.7%. This maximum concentration was obtained from photobioreactor using a 1000 lux halogen lamp with CO₂ supply after 7 hours illumination. The Oxygen concentration measuring device that had been designed gave 1,383 % of MSE. This result was obtained by comparing the result of designed device to reference device (Gas Alert Microclip).

Keywords: Photobioreactor, Microalgae *Chlorella vulgaris*, Hallogen Lamp, Blue LED, LM35 SK-25F Oxygen sensor.

1. INTRODUCTION

The effect of Global warming keep increasing these days as the emerging of factories in the world that produce the industrial waste such as the greenhouse gases including CO₂ gas emission. Gas CO₂ is the most contributed gas in global warming phenomena which is about 50%. meanwhile, other gases such as CFC_s, CH₄, O₃ and NO give contribution about 20%, 15%, 8%, and 7% [4]. Fossil fuels burning produced billion tons CO₂ gas globally every year. So that, the sunlight that was absorbed by earth's surface could not be reflected back to surface. Then it all reemitted back to the earth's surface in all direction and cause the climate change. CO₂ was the main emission (90% of the total emission) that was released into the air when forest fires happen [6]. So the emission of CO₂ gave significant effect of the air quality.

There were several mitigations that have been conducted to mitigate the CO₂ as one of the contributors of global warming, such as the development of bioreactor using microalgae [2]. Microalgae is chloroplast organism which produce Oxygen through Photosynthesis process. The

abundant quantity of microalgae and its convenience cultivation, make it feasible to be one of renewable resources. Microalgae is considered effective in reducing CO₂ emission through the photosynthesis process because of its natural process and environmentally friendly ^[7]. Meanwhile, Oxygen is needed by human and other creatures to breathe and respire. And the plants also need Oxygen to respiratory and nutrient absorbing process.

One of microalgae species that was usually used in mitigating CO₂ gas emission is *Chlorella vulgaris*. *Chlorella vulgaris* is easy to be found almost all over Indonesia, and its photosynthesis can occur using artificial light source ^[2]. It is also durable with 60 days life expectancy comparing to other microalgae ^[5].

Photobioreactor is bioreactor that is combined with certain light source as energy intake into reactor. Microalgae can be used as reactor of photobioreactor. And photosynthesis is the reaction that is occurred in photobioreactor. Technically, photobioreactor uses CO₂ gas emission which is injected into it. Photobioreactor contains microalgae with water (H₂O) as culture media. Microalgae absorbs CO₂ and produces Oxygen (O₂) with light energy from the light source. Then the produced Oxygen is released into the air. Oxygen concentration measuring device is needed to measure the Oxygen concentration that is produced by photobioreactor. And the temperature controller is also needed, because it can cause the microalgae to die if the temperature is not kept in certain temperature range.

The using of microalgae photobioreactor to optimize the Oxygen (O₂) concentration and CO₂ gas emission mitigation had been developed by several researchers ^{[7][3][8]}. First photobioreactor^[7] was designed with tubular photobioreactor for industrial sector using *Chlorella sp.* CO₂ concentration that had optimally absorbed were $2,3 \pm 0,91\%$ at 1,5 l/min CO₂ flow rate and $1,5 \pm 0,47\%$ at 2 l/min CO₂ flow rate. But They did not measure the Oxygen concentration that was produced by photobioreactor. The second photobioreactor^[3] was designed in flat-plate form using *Chlorella vulgaris* microalgae with CO₂ supply and measured the produced Oxygen concentration. But They did not vary the light source too. The third photobioreactor^[8] was designed in tubular form using *Spirulina sp.* But They did not vary the light source. So, We were unable to see which light intensities condition that photobioreactor can produce the optimum Oxygen concentration. Moreover, all the development photobioreactor mentioned above was not equipped with temperature controller.

Based on the lack of previous photobioreactor developments, We developed *Chlorella vulgaris* microalgae photobioreactor to optimize the production of Oxygen (O₂) as well to mitigate the abundant of CO₂. Photobioreactor was designed in tubular form. By varying CO₂ supplies i.e. 0,5 l/min and with no supply of CO₂. So we can examine the difference effect by varying CO₂ supply. This photobioreactor was illuminated by blue LED, halogen lamp and sunlight. Oxygen (O₂) concentration that was produced in every light condition will be compared one to another. Photobioreactor temperature was controlled with controller device. The purpose of controlling photobioreactor temperature was because microalgae was able to live in (25-35)°C temperature range. Moreover the photobioreactor was also combined with Oxygen measuring device to measure the production of Oxygen concentration. To check the accuracy of Oxygen concentration measuring device, the result of measurement from designed device was compared to the reference measuring device (Gas Alert Microchip).

2. METHOD

2.1 The Cultivation of Microalgae

Initial cultivation of *Chlorella vulgaris* microalgae 250 ml for microalgae was *Bold Bassal Medium* (BBM). This method used 15 types of nutrient i.e. 10 ml nutrients that consisted of K₂HPO₄, KH₂PO₄, MgSO₄·7H₂O, NaNO₃, CaCl₂·2H₂O, Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, CuSO₄·5H₂O, ZnSO₄·7H₂O, MnCl₂·4H₂O, H₂SO₄, NaCl. 3 nutrients that consisted of 1 ml FeSO₄·7H₂O, KOH, EDTA dan 0,7 ml H₂BO₃. All 15 Nutrients were dissolved in 1000 ml aquades. then dissolved nutrients was being sterilized using autoclave for about 15 minutes. The *Bold Bassal Medium* (BBM) method is pretty easy to do since the nutrients were easy to be found. The initial cultivation process of *Chlorella vulgaris* 250 ml could be seen on Figure 1

Figure 1. Microalgae cultivation

Microalgae maximally grow for 10 days. During the growth period microalgae was being aerated by air pump.

2.2 The Measurement of *Chlorella vulgaris* Absorbance Using UV-Vis Spectrophotometer

We measured the *Chlorella vulgaris* absorbance to examine the spectrums that can be absorbed by microalgae in UV-Vis range. As we can see on Figure 2, microalgae reach the maximum absorbance in its photosynthesis process at 450 nm spectrum, which is in visible light spectrum. So this is why we choose LED as the light source to optimize the photosynthesis proses of microalgae on photobioreactor.

Figure 2. The spectrum absorbance graph of *Chlorella vulgaris* microalgae

2.3 The Design of Temperature Controller

The temperature controller was designed to keep the photobioreactor temperature in (25-35)^oC. The controller used two LM35 sensors, and each one of them was placed in photobioreactor with CO₂ supply and without CO₂ supply. Temperature controller was equipped with fan that was connected to relay. Relay will be active and automatically turn the fan on whenever temperature reach 35^oC point. Relay will be automaticly inactive and automaticly turn off the fan whenever the temperature drop to 25^oC point. the temperature of photobioreactor was displayed on 16 x 2 LCD. And the temperature controller used Arduino Uno R3 as the data processor. The circuit of temperature controller was shown on Figure 3.

Figure 6. The schematic of Oxygen sensor characterization

The Oxygen sensor and reference device were placed side by side right under the Oxygen tube chimney. The output voltage of sensor was compared to the measured Oxygen concentration value that was obtained from reference device.

2.6 The Design of Photobioreactor

We measured the Oxygen concentration of three types of photobioreactor. The differences of each photobioreactor was based on the light source that were used. We used Hallogen Lamp and Blue LED as the light source. Hallogen lamp was chosen as the light source because of its characteristic resemble the sunlight. Meanwhile blue LED was good for photosynthesis because of its spectrum range (400-500 nm.. Which we have seen from Figure, microalgae has the maximum absorbance in this range. All photobioreactor had the same dimension i.e height 50 cm and diameter 10 cm. they were placed in light chamber with dimension 40 cm x 50 cm x 60 cm . The cambers were coated by alumunium foil to avoid the contamination light from outside chamber. So, the photobioreactor can be illuminated effectifely. Each photobioreactor contained 1250 mL of cultivated microalgae.

Figure 7. The design of photobioreactor (a) with Hallogen as the light source; (b) with blue LED as the light source

Light intensities of hallogen light were varied at 1000 lux, 3000 lux dan 5000 lux. Those were the intensities of light where microalgae optimumly to cultivate^[3]. The light intensities were set by using dimmer lamp. The light intensity was varied to examine the optimum Oxygen concentration that would be produced by Chlorella vulgaris microalgae.

One of photobioreactor was supplied with 0,5 l/min CO₂ and the other one was not. We varied the suply of CO₂ to examine which kind of CO₂ condition that caused the photobioreactor produce the optimum concentration of Oxygen.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 SK-25F Sensor Characterization Data

The initial testing of the linearity of SK-25F Oxygen sensor by examine the comparison of voltage output of sensor to Oxygen concentration from reference device. the output voltage of sensor was obtained using digital multimeter. Figure shows the linearity graph of sensor output to Oxygen concentration

Figure 8. The correlation between output voltage of sensor and Oxygen concentration

The linear regression of sensor is $y = 0,3025x - 2,748$. For every the rising of 1% Oxygen concentration value caused the 0,3025 mV change of output voltage of sensor. The degree of linear correlation that was obtained $R^2 = 0,9807$. It shows that the output of SK-25F sensor has good linearity. The transfer function that was obtained from the result of sensor characterization would be input to microcontroler program list.

3.2 The Result of LM35 Temperature Sensor Characterization

To obtained the accurate value in measuring and controlling photobioreactor temperature, we characterized the sensor output to termometer first. Figure 9 Shows the Correlation value of output voltage of two sensors to termometer.

Figure 9. The characterization graph of LM35 output voltage

The regression of two sensors approached 1.0 i.e 0.9986 and 0,9947. Those value show the good liniarity of sensors. The transfer function of each sensor was input to the Arduino IDE program, so the temperature controler work accurately.

3.3 The Result of Non-Inverting Amplifier Circuit Output

The output voltage of Oxygen sensor which is still in mV scale must be amplified before being transferred to Arduino Uno. The comparison of output voltage of preamplified sensor and sensor after being amplified can be senn in Table 1.

Table 1. The output voltage of sensor and non inverting amplifier circuit

Oxygen Concentration (%)	Preamplified Output Voltage of Oxygen Sensor (mV)	The Amplified Output Voltage of Oxygen Sensor (V)
20,90	3,84	1,5
23,10	4,9	1,7
25,30	5,9	2,1
26,70	6,7	2,2
28,40	7,3	2,4

3.4 The Result of Oxygen Concentration Device with SK-25F Sensor

The photobioreactor was being equipped by a designed Oxygen concentration device. To verify the accuracy of the designed device, we compared the value of the designed device to the reference device. The comparison of those two was described in graph on Figure 9.

Figure 9. The comparison measurement result of reference device and disigned device

It can be seen from the graph, the result of designed device and the reference device gave the close value from measurement. The total MSE of the designed device was 1.383 %. So, the performance of device gave the accurate measurement result.

3.5 The Oxygen Concentration Result of Photobioreactor

The concentration of Oxygen was recorded in every 3/7 hours illumination. This method of measurement was set to examine how the illumination period affect Oxygen concentration production.

Figure 10. The concentration Oxygen produced by photobioreactor with different light source

It can be seen from the graph on Figure 10 the Oxygen concentration from the photobioreactor with CO₂ supply was described with blue graph and without CO₂ supply was described with orange graph. We can see that for each light intensity or light source variation, the optimum Oxygen concentration was gained from the photobioreactor with CO₂ supply. This was because the photosynthesis process was optimum when the amount of CO₂ increase.

The optimum oxygen concentration was gained after 7 hours illumination. So, the period of illumination affect the production of Oxygen concentration. The longer illumination the higher Oxygen concentration produced by photobioreactor. The value of light intensity also affected the production of Oxygen concentration. We can see from the graph, when the photobioreactor was illuminated by the 1000 lux hallogen, photoboreactor produced 21.7% Oxygen. So it was the most effective light intensity to use to produce the optimum Oxygen concentration. Meanwhile, in condition with no light photobioreactor only produced 19,6% Oxygen as the maximum amount. Hallogen lamp and blue LED are good to be chosen as the light source for photobioreactor. Because they could optimize the photosynthesis process, by comparing the Oxygen concentration amount described on graphs on Figure 10. But it is necessary to set the intensity of light to gain optimum amount of Oxygen. Figure 11 Shows the hardware of photobioreactor that has been developed.

Figure 11. The integrated system of photobioreactor

4. CONCLUSION

1. The developed photobioreactor has the good performance in optimizing Oxygen concentration production and absorbing CO₂. So, it is good to be chosen as one of effective way in mitigating CO₂ gas.
2. The temperature controller work well in controlling the photobioreactor temperature to be in (25-35) °C condition.
3. The most optimum Oxygen concentration produced was 21.7%. Which was produced by photobioreactor with CO₂ supply at the 1000 lux Hallogen illumination. And the lowes value of Oxygen concentration was produced by photobioreactor in no light condition. So, it is important to set the light intensity to optimize the Oxygen concentration production. And it can be concluded that photobioreactor work well whenever it is supplied by CO₂, so it is effective as the CO₂ mitigation.
4. The designed Oxygen concentration measuring device worked well too, with RMS= 1.383 %.

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